

CHAOTIC SECULAR INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Nationalism and religion has been the subject of debate in India for the past few decades. Religion in this context will be understood as an individual activist and therefore a political tool.

Secularism is India's national system and is known as the only way to ensure religious and cultural diversity. It provides a place to ensure cultural and religious diversity and to support a culture full of "unity in diversity". Indian secularism emerged as a political ideology in the middle of the 20th century, to preserve religious and cultural diversity to allow India to curb social competition and develop as a modern republic of the country. This paper seeks to discover the historical variability of this world power. It faces questions such as these: What is the state of India's resistance? Is it a real social and political reality, or is it just a theoretical concept? This paper, therefore, attempts to examine whether the political view of intolerance provides a basis for affirming the religious and cultural diversity of India, especially given the current political advantages of Hindutva and Sangh Parivar.

India, widely known for its intertwined religions and democracies, is home to 1.4 billion people. It is alarming and astonishing at the same time that India is home to about one-sixth of the world's population, which includes not only a large number of Hindus but also a large Muslim population, which ranks second only to Indonesia. It is a country where social status is marked by equal parts of cultural diversity and religious enmity, as well as the religion that has become a bone of social and political conflict.

Although the terms "Secularism" and "Secular" did not exist in the Constitution at the time of its inception, it provided and ensured freedom and equality in all

religions. The spirit of religious equality, religious tolerance, and religious freedom was enshrined in the Constitution from the outset.

The Right to Religious Freedom¹ falls under Part III of the Constitution which forms its basic framework. It can be clearly stated that Secularism is an undeniable element of the Constitution. The repeated emphasis on this fact is Judiciary. However, the term "State" was eventually incorporated into the Constitution by Amendment Act 42, 1976.

WHAT IS SECULARISM?

The concept of Secularism in its literal sense implies the separation of the Nation from religious institutions.

According to the late author Khushwant Singh, Secularism has two meanings: the Western view distinguishes between state functions (including political), and religious functions, limited to public or private houses of worship. This is the philosophy Nehru embraced, preached, and lived by. One reason was that all religions should be treated equally. This was taught and seen by men like Mahatama Gandhi and Maulana Azad, and it continued for as long as the two men were alive.

After that, it turned into a religious show. To demonstrate human neutrality, a devout Hindu visited the Islamic Dargah or performed the Iftar feast. Celebrate Diwali with your Hindu friends if you were a Muslim. Nationalism has been reduced to a challenge. Concerning religion, the time has proved that Nehru was right; Gandhi and Azad were wrong.

¹ INDIAN CONSTITUTION Article 25 & Article 28

WHAT DOES IT MEAN TO BE SECULAR?

In the case of *Indira Nehru Gandhi v Raj Narain*², the Supreme Court of India held that secularism means that the state has no religion of its own and that all citizens of the country have the same right to freedom of conscience and the freedom to profess, practice, and propagates any religion. Strictly speaking, secular unbelief includes the complete separation of Religion and State.

How can Indian courts, while claiming to be secular, recognize the Shari'ah-based Islamic Law?³ If provincial governments and governments were not secular, how could they take over the operation of Hindu temples? How could the government of the country provide financial assistance for religious institutions to operate religiously? How could the world government organize and amend Hindu law? If the government were a part of the world, how could it be possible to increase the status quo?

FAITHS

WHO ARE HINDUS?

Indigenous peoples (especially Greeks and Persians) coined the term "Hindu" to refer to the people living across the Indus / Sindhu River. Hindus today worship various gods and form complex social organizations. Hindu beliefs are the same because they believe that Brahma, or the Divine, is omnipresent in the human race, that consciousness lasts a long time, and that one's actions will contribute to the soul's subsequent transformation of the human body.

² *Indira Nehru Gandhi v Raj Narain* AIR 1975 SCR (3) 333

³ Sharia acts as a code for living that all Muslims should adhere to

Vidyosha student of BSC economic honors, currently studying at Christ University identifies herself as Hindu. For her, her religion, and her faith comes first then her nation. According to her, the nation has given them exodus, oppression, forced converging, and mob lynching of her community.

She remembered the Kashmiri Pandit⁴ exodus where 4000 Kashmiri Hindus were murdered by Muslims present there. She even gave the example of Godhara⁵ train case. And how all the mob lynching against Hindus and mocking the deities have been normalized by both masses and politicians. So for her India is not a secular country but a showcase of it.

Any pilgrimage would not be supported by a completely secular nation. However, in 2012, the Indian government paid out Rs 836 crores in subsidies for the Hajj. The government must phase away this subsidy within 10 years, according to a Supreme Court ruling. Shouldn't the state finance religious pilgrimages of all kinds if it is so eager to do so? Why Amarnath Yatras and Kumbh Melas aren't given the same kind of subsidies?

Before critics claim that the government overspends on security for Amarnath Yatra or Kumbh Mela pilgrims, I would emphasize that protecting citizens is not a favor but rather a fundamental duty of any state.

Temples are under government jurisdiction, but not mosques or churches.

The Hindu Religious and Charitable Endowment Act⁶ allow state governments to take over temples and control their vast properties & assets.

Strangely, the state government is permitted to use the funds raised by a temple (donations, income from assets, etc.) for projects that have nothing to do with

⁴ The Exodus of Kashmiri Hindus, or Pandits, in early-1990 migration

⁵ Burning of S6 coach of Sabarmati Express train at Godhra on February 27, 2002

⁶ Madras Hindu Religious Endowments Act, 1923 (Act I of 1925) Acts of Parliament, 1923 (India)

the temple, any other temples, or even Hindus or Hinduism! Interestingly, none of this applies to gurdwaras, mosques, or churches. A non-Hindu place of worship cannot be taken over by the government under any circumstances. In which universe is this fair, I wonder as I type this. I also think, "What business does the government have in houses of worship?" I have no solutions.

DIFFERENT LAWS FOR HINDUS, MUSLIMS, AND CHRISTIANS

In a truly secular country, all citizens irrespective of religion would be covered by a single set of laws. In India, however, people of different religious beliefs are covered by different laws. While Hindus, Sikhs, and Buddhists are covered by the Hindu code bills (Hindu Marriage Act, Hindu Succession Act, etc.), Muslims are covered by Muslim Personal laws, and Christians are covered by Christian Personal laws. So, Hindus, Muslims, Christians & Parsis inherit property differently; have different rules for marriage, divorce, and adoption among other things. After all this, the matter of intolerance has also been an important topic of discussion.

The best example was the demolishing of Babri Masjid⁷, the demolition of the Babri Masjid was illegally carried out on 6 December 1992 by a large group of activists of the Vishva Hindu Parishad and allied organizations. How most of the young so-called Hindus in the name of religion not only illegally demolished the holy place of Muslims but also incited communal violence in which around 2000 people died mainly Muslims.

Isn't it ironic that those people were chanting "JAI SHREE RAM" while creating chaos and spreading hatred? They call themselves a devotee of ram (RAM BHAKTS), Ram who was the idol of a calm and composed mind. I feel

⁷ December 6, 1992, kar sevaks started attacking Muslim residents of Ayodhya, ransacking and demolishing their houses

if Ram today comes down and sees these rioters who call themselves his devotee, he will not only feel bad but also question his path of life because he was never a supporter of invalid violence, and how he calmly handled the Parshuram. Then it must not be the religion that taught them this much hate.

When we talk about hate and if we are not talking about the Tabrez Ansari mob lynching case, it will be injustice, and it is only the government's right to perpetuate injustice in Jharkhand, India, on June 17, 2019, a lynch mob attacked Tabrez Ansari, 24. Ansari, a Muslim, was violently beaten, tied to a tree, and made to sing mantras from the Hindu religion. 4 days later, he passed away. After a video of the lynching went viral, people were aware of the occurrence. He was accused of bike theft by the assailants. The case's facts are straightforward, but what stands out is the intensity of the hatred directed at the individual, whose surname was Muslim. Not as a thief, but as a Muslim, it was perceived as a criminal. The police were informed in the early hours of June 18. Ansari was taken into custody and imprisoned at the Saraykela Police Station. He called his wife and informed her of the incident. She told her family members.

Residents requested that Ansari receive medical attention, but the police instead sent him to jail without it. Ansari was unable to speak when his uncle visited him in prison two days later. His uncle claimed that he requested medical assistance from the police but was turned down. He made attempts to speak with the prison's medical officer as well but was unsuccessful. Ansari's family learned on the morning of June 22 that his health was critical and that he had been admitted to Sadar Hospital. His relatives reached the hospital by 7:30 am, but by that time, he had died.

Now who is responsible for his death, the Religion, the so-called "Ram Bhakts" or the authority? Religious books talk about nonviolence and respect for others

that's why ram touched Ravan's feet after the fight, so religion is not the issue, the issue is PREJUDICE, HATE, INTOLERANCE, and the HUMANS. Humans who don't even know about their religion but always are in front to question other religions, filled with hate and using religion as a weapon to not even spread hate but kill the faith of others. These so-called Hindus who go on the streets of democracy and kill secularism with so much pride are so illiterate to even know about their faith. Hinduism gave Ram, the most dignified person in the whole history who was loyal to his wife and his dharma, Hinduism gave Krishna, one who taught Arjuna how to forgive, and Hinduism gave Draupadi, one who was born out of the fire with a calm mind like a sandal. Rather than following their path, people manipulate them for their interest and their interest lies with hate.

Sati Pratha, a culture in Hinduism that was used to practiced by women in Mughals time to protect themselves, as barbaric Mughals used to kidnap the Rajput women and rape or keep them as a prostitute but as we move towards colonialism we saw the step that was taken up in helplessness has become now a notion or expectations from all the Hindu women. The term sati pratha has nowhere written in any holy book of Hinduism, so it's Hindu human beings who tweaked their religion to hurt the people of their religion.

Hinduism also has a caste system. In reality, there is no caste, there are varnas. There is 4 varna, The varnas have been known since a hymn in the Rigveda (the oldest surviving Indian text) that portrays the Brahman, the Kshatriya, the Vaishya, and the Shudra. And according to Rigveda, it's the qualities or characteristics of a human that determines his varna not birth. A mere birth cannot decide whether that person is learned or not. Everyone is allowed to read Vedas and understand it. Understanding the Vedas and implying them in real life determines your varna. But again caste system came which gave birth system and it is understandable as no one will be able to adapt to the lifestyle of

real Brahmin, no one can leave the worldly lust, and no one is tolerant of other's ideologies, in the same way, no one can be Khstariya because no one is warrior rather everyone is a coward who satisfies their hate by killing a man mere just because he was of either other cast or other religion. And again they dare to come up on stage and say they believe in non-violence, I want to ask whether they will be able to look into the eyes of Tabrez Ansari's wife and say that they do not have any hatred for their religion.

Hinduism has a long history, and most of its major religious and philosophical writings date back to 1000 BC. In the middle of the millennium, Mahavira, the founder of Jainism, and Buddha, the founder of Buddhism, introduced two new religions. Buddhism benefited from royal patronage from the Maurya dynasty, the first Hindu empire that ruled most of the Indian subcontinent under Ashoka in the 3rd century BC. Buddhism began to decline with the rise of Hinduism during the Gupta dynasty in the 4th century AD. Meanwhile, by the 15th century, another religion had emerged in Punjab, Sikh.

So it is very evident that Hinduism is a kind of mother to many other religions and a mother cannot be wrong or this intolerant towards others. It's all because of the fake or pseudo-Hindus who are unfortunately even representing the whole religion as they are part of the authority. We as a human but keeping religion aside just for once need to see the authenticity of any actions. A mere difference of opinion cannot be the reason to kill anyone.

WHAT IS ISLAM IN INDIA?

Ozma is a student of Economics honors currently studying at Christ University Delhi NCR. She identifies herself as a Muslim. (Surprisingly both Vidyosha and Ozma are roommates and living peacefully in the same room for the last 1 year).

One more thing that surprised me was that for Ozma also, this country is not a secular country. She feels discriminated against and has been asked several times to move to Pakistan. Why Pakistan? Why that place where Indian Muslims are been treated worse than any dogs and why move out of their own country who do these people are to decide who will live in India and who will not?

She recalled the entire barbaric incident that has happened to her community by other religions, the Gujarat riots⁸. Where 790- 1926 Muslims were killed, I am waiting for someone to come up and say "Hindus also were being killed" that does not justify the trauma these people will hold for life. And since when the concept of blame games started and how these blame games help people to satisfy their hate is what attracted me the most.

1987 HASHIMPURA MASSACRE⁹

During the Hindu-Muslim riots in Meerut city, Uttar Pradesh state, India, on May 22, 1987, 19 members of the Provincial Armed Constabulary (PAC) are accused of rounding up 42 Muslim youth from the Hashimpura mohalla (locality), transporting them in a truck to the city's outskirts, where they were shot and then killed before having their bodies dumped in water canals. A few days later, floating corpses were discovered in the canals. 16 of the 19 accused turned themselves in May 2000; the other three were already deceased. They were all later released on bail. The Supreme Court of India ordered that the case's trial be moved from Ghaziabad to a Sessions Court in the Tis Hazari complex in Delhi in 2002 because it was the oldest case still pending there. The

⁸ The 2002 Gujarat riots, also known as the 2002 Gujarat violence and the Gujarat pogrom, were three days of inter-communal violence in the western Indian state of Gujarat.

⁹ The Hashimpura massacre was the killing of 50 Muslim men by police on or around 22 May 1987 near Meerut in Uttar Pradesh state, India, during the 1987 Meerut communal riots

Tis Hazari Court declared all 16 of the persons convicted in the 1987 Hashimpura massacre case to be exonerated on March 21, 2015, citing a lack of evidence. The Court underlined that none of the accused PAC employees could be recognized by the survivors. 16 PKK employees were found guilty and given life sentences by the Delhi High Court on October 31, 2018, overturning the lower court's decision.

But does this justify the amount of hate they are holding against others? Everyone is still waiting for someone to give one reason to kill a Minor Hindu boy Rupesh Pandey by a Muslim gang while going to attend the Saraswati Puja procession. The parent's only son, Rupesh Kumar Pandey, 17, was on his way to the Saraswati Puja procession on a Sunday evening. Little did he and his family know that the celebration would soon end with the death of a young man. A gang of four young Muslims attacked Rupesh for unknown reasons in the village of Kariyadpur under the Barkha police station in the Hazaribagh district. Rupesh, who was seriously injured, was taken to the hospital but died.

A religion (Islam) that has a proper code of conduct even for a war, where women, old, and children are not allowed to be touched and followers of that religion have killed a small boy. How will they manage to look up to the eyes of Allah at the time of doom and call themselves good Muslims? Simply because you have a long beard or you pray 5 times, will not justify you as a good Muslim.

WHAT IS TERRORISM?

Unlawful violence or threat of unlawful violence to inculcate fear for political or social aims. Did we notice in this whole definition, that there was no religious word being mentioned? Then who decided what terrorism is and what

not? Isn't untouchability terrorism? Isn't assaulting tribal people a form of terrorism? Or people can't see something else than an Islamic terrorism

Big authorities (politicians) say that they respect Muslims and welcome them, who gave them the right to welcome Muslims in their own homes.

There is a beautiful couplet "how will we convince them to ours? They don't consider us as their kin". US and THEM. Tragically this paper is not about Tabrez Ansari or Pehlu khan. This paper is about US and THEM. Whenever there is an accusation that "there are more kids in their community, or literacy is low" people tend to laugh, they laugh because all these problems are in some other community not in them. A country is cannot be divided into parts by drawing lines on paper, it is divided in our minds, by color, language, and religion, and tragically our politicians have divided this country into US and THEM very beautifully. And it is citizen's punishment that these politicians have announced before any judiciary could give a verdict. They have taught them the same bias that they (politicians, extremists) believe. This secularism is based on prejudice.

A country where people speak 150 languages, and follow any religion. How can someone do justice with the bias between US and THEM?

Gandhi was not killed by a community; rather he was killed by a human, so we can't blame his community for his crime. Terrorism is a criminal act, not a communal act. If every Muslim is weighed on the same weighing scale, then one-fourth of the population of this world will be under suspicion. We have to find another way, the country can stand by being divided, and all of us are part of this country.

Terrorists are not agents of Islam, but they are misusing Islam. If we acknowledge this fact, we will find out a way to escape from it.

The bomb blast is a part of terrorism but there are many more things that are seen as terrorism .like cast discrimination, tribe oppression, etc. if we don't allow the lectures in temples and prayer in parliament, everything will be under control.

SECULARISM IN THE JUDICIAL WORLD

The term secularism is dynamic as opposed to static there cannot be a single viewpoint on this matter that will hold up for an extremely long period. The Court occasionally assigns different meanings to words. It advances secularism and tries it.

On account of *Sardar Taheruddin Syedna Sahib v. Province of Bombay*¹⁰ (AIR 1962 SC 853). The Supreme Court of India pronounced that 'Articles 25 and 26 highlights the Indian majority rules government's common nature, which the principal architects, considered being vital to the Constitution's center establishment.

The Supreme Court announced in *Kesavananda Bharati v. Territory of Kerala*¹¹ (AIR 1973 SC1461) that secularism was a part of the Constitution's fundamental stricture. The Constitution's mainstream component, as indicated by Chief Justice Sikri, is its embodiment. The crucial pieces of the fundamental system, as per Justice Shelatand and Justice Grover, are the Constitution's mainstream and government nature. "Freedom of thought, articulation, conviction, confidence, and love couldn't be changed at any expense since they were important for the Constitution's center components," Justice Jaganmohan Reddy said.

¹⁰ *Sardar Taheruddin Syedna Sahib v. Province of Bombay* AIR (1962) SC 853 (1962)

¹¹ *Kesavananda Bharati v. Territory of Kerala* AIR, (1973) SC1461

The Court was asked the question of *Abhiram Singh v. C D Commachem*¹² whether secularism involves total partition of religion and governmental issues. The Court decided that secularism doesn't infer that the public authority ought to disregard religion; rather, it ought to treat all religions similarly. Religion and position are significant parts of our general public, and they can't be isolated from governmental issues altogether. The Supreme Court decided that secularism is the underpinning of the Constitution and thus can't be changed.

Secularism depends on the social value of protesting and ensuring that all religions are treated equally. In India no religion will be threatened as a public authority will not be affiliated with any trust. The Court further stated that there is a central link between secularism and a majority government, assuming that we believe a vote-based system would work and that gatherings should not be judged. The high price is beneficial; we want a traditional state. While Indian democracy has generally operated as a secular majority rule system, its reliability is questionable. In some cases, the state is said to favor a particular religion against the idea of secularism.

CITIZENSHIP AMENDMENT ACT (CAA), 2019

The Citizenship (Amendment) Act 2019 (CAA) is a controversial issue; On the one hand, it goes into the Constitution because it goes against the idea of secularism, while the Indian government ensures that it is sacred. Critics of the CAA say the organization abuses the idea of secularism by granting citizenship to visitors from the Hindu, Sikh, Buddhist, Christian, Jain, and Parsi groups who appear at the CAA. This country no later than December 31, 2014, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Afghanistan however reject Muslims.

¹² *Abhiram Singh v. C D Commachem* AIR 1996 SCC (3) 665

It is additionally contended to be biased in character, as it abuses both Article 14 and Article 15(1) of the Indian Constitution. Article 14 of the Indian Constitution proclaims unequivocally that the state will not decline any person inside India's region equity under the watchful eye of the law or equivalent treatment under the law. As per Article 15(1), the state will not victimize any individual exclusively based on religion, race, position, sex, the spot of birth, or any mix of these variables. It has been guaranteed that because "individual" is utilized in this article, it safeguards the two residents and non-residents.

The position put out by the Central Government is that conceding citizenship to anybody is a political matter that is neither enemy of common nor unfair. On account of the State of West Bengal versus Anwar Ali Sarkar, the Supreme Court of India pronounced that while Article 14¹³. Boycotts segregation, it considers a fair arrangement. In any case, the characterization ought to be founded on coherent differentia, and the grouping ought to hold back nothing

The CAA is a regulation that safeguards people in three lining countries from strict mistreatment: Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Afghanistan which are all Islamic states where radicalization is on the ascent, and Hindus, Sikhs, Buddhists, Jains, Parsis, and Christians persevere through strict oppression. Accordingly, there is a perceptible contrast between Muslims and different religions.

THE CONCLUSION

India is recognized around the world as a secular country. Secularism is a type of government where the state is intended to be fair in strict issues and not favor one religion over another.

¹³ INDIAN CONSTITUTION Article 14

The Citizenship (Amendment) Act, 2019, was presented in 2019 by the Central Government to safeguard the interests of six religions confronting strict mistreatment in three adjoining Islamic nations, however, it was met with solid resistance from different gatherings who asserted that its rejection of Muslims was unfair and conflicted with the idea of secularism, which is the groundwork of India's Constitution

If one inquires about the recent developments in the country regarding religious tolerance among Hindus and the view of Secularism, one should consider the changing demographics by religion, culture, and politics. What does one see when studying South Asian statistics? Hindus make up about 15% of the population when Pakistan was founded in 1947 but dropped to 1.6 percent in 1998.

Some people view the Hindu revival by mistake through the lens of Narendra Modi and the BJP. To understand the fundamental conflict between Abraham's and Dharmic thought, one must go back to the basic conflict between Abraham's and Dharmic thought. Dharmic philosophy is plural in nature. It covers a wide range of facts. A total of 33 million gods can be divided into one family. Whenever someone tries to divide us into US and THEM, go home and check the calendar, check how many days are left in elections.

Without a doubt, India does not have a theocracy, but it does have hypocrisy. Muslims and Christians of today cannot be held responsible for crimes committed in the past that they were not a part of. In truth, a large portion of today's Muslims and Christians are sprung from people who were formerly persecuted and converted under duress.

Change your outlook and the world become clearer to you.

Inquilab Zindabad

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